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Integral Optical Monitoring Camera (OMC) **Report on the technical tests performed at the end of the scientific operations**

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1 Introduction: the Optical Monitoring Camera (OMC) on Integral

The Optical Monitoring Camera (OMC) is one of the instruments onboard the Integral mission, launched in October 2002. It consists of an optical system focused onto a large format CCD detector working in frame transfer mode. The layout of the OMC camera unit is shown in Fig. 1. The optics is based on a refractive system with entrance pupil of 50 mm, focal length of 154 mm, and a field of view of $5 \times 5 \text{ deg}^2$. The optical design consists of six radiation-hard glass lenses (F/3) housed in a titanium barrel. The filter assembly holds two colored filters (Schott BG39 and GG495) defining a V filter (passband centered at 550 nm). An additional BK7G18 glass plate protects the filters from radiation. The optical throughput of the system is slightly higher than 70% at this wavelength, and the CCD quantum efficiency within the V filter passband is around 88%. A pair of green LEDs within the optical cavity provide “Flat-Field” illumination of the CCD for spatial non-uniformities calibration. The combination of titanium for the lens barrel and invar for the focal plane cavity allowed to have an almost a-thermal design, with the system focused over a wide range of temperatures. This allowed to avoid any focusing mechanism.

The CCD (1024×2048 pixels) uses one section (1024×1024pixels) for imaging and the other one for frame transfer before readout. The frame transfer time of around 0.2 ms avoids the need for a mechanical shutter. The OMC chip is an EEV (now Teledyne) CCD47-20, with an imaging area of 133×133 mm. It required a full qualification program for space applications which was carried out by the OMC consortium. The CCD head is cooled by means of a passive radiator to an operational temperature of around $-70 \pm 10 \text{ C}$ degrees. We show in Fig. 2 the Qualification Model EEV 47-20 CCD mounted on its support. More information about OMC can be found in Mas-Hesse et al. (2003) and Kuulkers et al. (2021).

Figure 1.- Internal design of the OMC.

Figure 2.- The CCD QM mounted on its structure, showing the copper thermal strap acting as a cold finger attached to the radiator.

2 Molecular condensation on the OMC CCD surface.

As shown in Fig. 2, the CCD detector is located within the focal plane cavity, with a cold finger directly attached to it. This cold finger is connected to an external radiator, so that the CCD temperature has been maintained below -60 C during the last 22^+ years (Fig. 3). By design, the CCD became the coldest surface within the focal plane cavity and, as such, was prone to be affected by the condensation of any volatiles remaining within the cavity, for example by outgassing from any material. To minimize the effects of condensation, a heater (the so-called “OMC baking heater”) was activated few hours after launch, and remained active during 2.6 days. Indeed, the first Flat-Field images taken by OMC during commissioning showed no condensation on the surface of the CCD at all.

Figure 3.- Evolution of the CCD temperatures (blue and pink correspond to the 2 thermistors located close to the CCD). Note that the temperature of the CCD has remained stable below -60C during all this time, except for the initial and final bakeouts of the CCD to $+40\text{ C}$.

Though the flat field images taken as soon as the OMC was activated didn't show any trace of condensation, the relative sensitivity of different areas of the CCD started to show some kind of evolution in the forthcoming months, as shown in Fig. 4:

- First, the central part of the CCD passed by various phases of becoming more and less sensitive than the average value. The ring formed in the external area showed a complementary behavior compared to the central region, becoming more sensitive when the central part loss sensitivity, and viceversa.
- Later on, some small spots appeared and slowly evolved to growing concentric ring structures alternating larger and lower relative sensitivities, slowly overcoming the

original big rings layout. When these structures extended over the whole surface of the CCD, the evolution slowed significantly and the relative sensitivity of the CCD has remained essentially stable during the last 18 years. This made it possible to correct the photometry for this effect after a careful determination of the Flat-Field matrix (which defines the relative response pixel by pixel of the CCD). The procedure to derive the Flat-Field matrix was improved with the time, combining images illuminated by the LEDs with sky images obtained on specific pointings where relatively large zodiacal light was expected, and following some dithering patterns to remove the effects of the stellar background.

Figure 4.- Evolution of the Flat-Field matrices over the years.

The preliminary analysis of the data led to the conclusion that a molecular deposition of material (probably water ice) on top of the antireflecting coating of the CCD, with non-uniform thickness (up to ~150 nm), might have induced variations of transparency leading to the observed relative changes in sensitivity. Alcione Mora (Telespazio UK for ESA, private communication) performed a number of simulations on the effect of a water ice layer of variable thickness on the sensitivity of a CCD similar to OMC's one. In Fig. 5 we show that a water ice layer with variable thickness up to around 100 nm can lead to variations in relative sensitivity within the Johnson V filter passband of the same order as we measured on the OMC (few percent). We therefore assume that the concentric structures define regions of ice with varying thickness, suggesting that the deposition of water molecules was not uniform over the CCD, and evolved with time.

Figure 5.- Effect of a layer of water ice of different thicknesses on the sensitivity of the CCD, as computed by Alcione Mora (Telespazio UK for ESA, private communication). The dotted line represents the transmission curve of the Johnson V OMC filter.

It is worth noting that the effect is enhanced by the fact that the OMC receives light only within the Johnson V filter band, centered at around 550 nm (not only has the OMC a V filter at its optical aperture, but the calibration was originally performed with 2 green LEDs emitting at 570 nm to mimic the effect of the V filter). As shown in Fig.5, the net effect of this thin layer of water ice is to shift the peak of the spectral response of the antireflecting coating by around 50 – 100 nm, therefore modifying the final amount of light absorbed by the CCD within the V filter. Using a broader passband or even white light, as is the case in other missions, would most likely have minimized this effect.

Since the condensation of ice stopped after ~4-5 years and the sensitivity pattern became very stable, we decided to minimize risks and did not activate the baking heaters again. These heaters are glued to the surface of the external radiator and the effects of increasing suddenly the

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temperature (from -80C to $+40\text{C}$) could have induced some permanent damages on the thermomechanical interfaces. Especially critical was the interface between the cold finger and the CCD packaging, since a good contact was needed to keep the CCD at working temperatures.

3 OMC technical tests

At the end of the scientific operations phase of Integral we asked ESA to perform a set of technical tests to gain information on the status and evolution of the instrument after more than 22 years in space, and to explore possible solutions to the problems discussed above. We proposed to activate the OMC baking heaters to test the effects of the bakeout on the detector. We also proposed to take some reference images to be compared with images of the same field obtained at the start of the operations in 2002, and to acquire images of one of the PLATO fields for future reference.

3.1 OMC CCD de-icing

We wanted to investigate whether increasing the CCD temperature above a certain value for a rather long time would evaporate the contamination, completely or partially, while keeping the integrity of the thermomechanical interfaces. If this were the case, we would also like to monitor whether the volatiles would condense again on the CCD surface after few weeks, acting as a cold trap, or whether the evaporated molecules would leave the cavity through the venting holes.

Similar de-icing procedures have been conducted on other missions. Plucinsky et al. (2004) analyzed how to best de-ice the cold filters on the Chandra ACIS instrument, concluding that “bakeout scenarios in which the focal plane temperature and the detector housing temperature are raised to $+20\text{ C}$ are the most likely to produce a positive outcome”. This is consistent with our conclusions during the design phase of the OMC, and the baking heaters were designed to reach temperatures on the CCD up to around $+40\text{C}$. Nevertheless, the baking was never performed on Chandra ACIS for safety reasons. On the other hand, the SOHO/EIT (Extreme ultraviolet Imaging Telescope) instrument warms up its CCD periodically (every ~ 3 months) by turning on small electric heaters, raising the CCD chip temperature to $\sim +16\text{C}$, to evaporate vapors/slush that condense on the detector (<https://www.esa.int/content/view/full/182106>). Furthermore, the WFPC2 on the HST (Wide Field and Planetary Camera 2) performed a routine decontamination procedure warming the camera's CCDs for about 6 hours, to evaporate UV-blocking contaminants that gradually accumulated on the cold detector windows (https://www.stsci.edu/hst/wfpc2/Wfpc2_hand_current/ch8_calibration15.html~). Initially, decontaminations were scheduled monthly to address the rapid contamination rate and throughput loss, but as the contamination rate decreased over the instrument's lifetime, the time interval between decontaminations was increased to about 49 days by Cycle 11. Other instruments also included de-icing procedures, like the SXT on Yokkoh, the ISS on Cassini or SUIT on Aditya-L1. More recently, ESA has performed de-icing of one of the mirrors on the Euclid mission by heating them by 35 C up to around -113 C , recovering more than 15% light collection (https://www.esa.int/ESA_Multimedia/Images/2024/03/First_results_of_Euclid_de-icing_campaign).

Therefore, though the thermal environment and physical conditions are clearly different, there is consensus that a bakeout of the cold surfaces affected by condensation of volatiles should effectively remove the condensed molecules, at least temporarily.

Conducting this activity required the following steps:

- Perform a standard Flat-Field procedure to take as a reference.
- Activate the baking heater during 2.7 days, while monitoring the CCD temperature readout within the standard TM.
- Deactivate the heater and wait until the CCD temperature is back below -60C.
- Perform a second standard Flat-Field procedure for comparison.
- Take an additional set of Flat-Field images a few weeks after the baking in order to verify the possible re-condensation of volatiles.

3.1.1 First set of reference Flat-Field images

The first set of Flat-Field reference images were taken during Integral revolution 2871, on January 19th, 2025. The transmission of some frames failed, but we got enough information to characterize the Flat-Field of the detector before the bakeout procedure. The following images were acquired (within parentheses the commanded number of frames):

- 3x3 raster sky images (9):
 - 5 out of 9 images fully transmitted
 - 2 only partially ~1/3, 2 lost
- First Dark Current Calibration images:
 - Completely lost
- Flat Field images
 - 0.5s LEDs (8): 7 out of 8 images transmitted
 - 0.5s sky (4): OK (small gap in one image, 61 packets lost)
 - Y_BIN=0 (8): OK
 - 220s sky (3): OK
- Second Dark Current Calibration images: OK

We show in Fig. 6 the resulting reference Flat-Field matrix just before the baking activity.

Figure 6.- Flat-Field reference matrix before the baking activity. Note that the deviations in relative sensitivity are in any case below $\pm 5\%$. To enhance the details in the figures of the Flat-Fields before and after the bakeout, the matrices shown were derived considering only the LED images.

3.1.2 Bakeout heater activation

The CCD bakeout heater was activated at the end of Integral revolution 2871, from January 20th, 2025 at 20:06 (UTC) to January 23rd, 2025 at 13:00 (UTC). It was active for ~2.7 days.

Figure 7.- Temperature profiles during the activations of the bakeout heater. Top left: first baking just after launch; top right: last baking in January 2025; bottom left: zoom to show the gradient of the temperature increase during the last baking, going from -80C to +20C in around 1h30m (as indicated by the green dotted lines), and reaching +40 after ~6 more hours; bottom right: evolution of the different temperature sensors during the last bakeout.

As shown in Fig. 7 the system reacted as designed 25 years ago. Note that the bakeout heaters are installed on the CCD radiator, and there is some temperature gradient from there to the CCD itself. This is evident from the inversion of the difference between the readings of the thermistors located in the radiator and on the cold finger, this one closer to the CCD, during nominal conditions and during the bakeouts. Due to a change in the attitude of the spacecraft, the temperature became a bit lower during the second half of the de-icing activity, but the temperature on the CCD itself was in any case above $\geq +30C$ during the whole process. Fig. 7 (bottom right) also shows that during the hotter phase of the baking the thermostats on the OMC lens barrel were not needed to keep the lenses at their nominal temperature.

3.1.3 Second set of Flat-Field images

The second set of Flat Field reference images were taken during Integral revolution 2873, on January 24th, 2025, shortly after the de-icing activity. The following images were obtained (within parentheses the commanded number of frames):

- 3x3 raster sky images (9): OK
- Dark Current Calibration images (10): OK
- Flat-Field images
 - 0.5s LEDs (8): OK (small gap in one image, 101 packets lost)
 - 0.5s sky (4): OK (small gap in one image, 47 packets lost)
 - Y_BIN=0 (8): OK
 - 220s sky (3): OK

We show in Fig. 8 the resulting Flat-Field matrix just after the baking activity. Note the gray levels scale, within a range ± 0.01 . The dispersion is much smaller than before the de-icing procedure.

Figure 8.- Flat-Field reference matrix after the baking activity, with enhanced contrast (± 0.01).

Finally, in Fig. 9 we compare the pre- (rev. 2871) and post- (rev. 2873) baking Flat-Field matrices with the one obtained during the commissioning phase in October 21st, 2002 (rev. 2).

Figure 9.- Comparison of the Flat-Field matrices derived before baking (left), after baking (middle) and just after launch in October 2002, shown with the same scale (± 0.05).

We conclude that the bakeout of the CCD was mostly (but still partially) successful by removing the inhomogeneities on the CCD relative sensitivity by a factor above 5, when compared to the Flat-Field taken just before. The remaining structure of the inhomogeneities observed three days after the bakeout (Fig. 9, middle panel) appear at a similar level than the intrinsic response inhomogeneities of the CCD observed after the bakeout performed after the launch (Fig. 9, right panel).

3.1.4 Final set of Flat Field images

The final set of Flat-Field reference images were taken 36 days after the bakeout, during Integral revolution 2886, on February 28th, 2025 (within parentheses the commanded number of frames):

- 3x3 raster sky images (9): OK
- Dark Current Calibration images (10): OK
- Flat Field images
 - 0.5s LEDs (8): OK
 - 0.5s sky (4): OK
 - Y_BIN=0 (8): OK
 - 220s sky (3): OK
- Second set of Dark Current Calibration images: OK

The corresponding Flat-Field matrix is shown in Fig. 10 (right). The Flat-Field matrix from rev. 2873 is also plotted for comparison (left). It became evident that just ~5 weeks after the baking, the condensation of volatiles was already re-starting on the CCD surface, once again affecting the relative sensitivity of the impacted pixels. As mentioned above, the effect of the condensation results in some pixels becoming relatively more sensitive than the average value, while others show a clear loss of sensitivity, still within a few percent range. This effect is discussed later in Sect. 4.1 analyzing the histograms of the Flat-Field matrix values.

Figure 10.- Flat-Field matrices taken just after de-icing on January 24th (left) and on February, 28th, 2025, 5 weeks after, both shown at the same scale (top panel: ± 0.05 , bottom panel: ± 0.01).

3.2 OMC reference images of the Cyg X-1 field

While the performance of the OMC (sensitivity, optical properties, CCD status, etc.) has been monitored closely during the 22⁺ years of operation, we asked ESA to repeat one of the first frames that were taken during the commissioning phase in November 2002 centered at Cyg X-1, aiming to perform a visual comparison of the 2 frames after such a long period of time.

12 images with different exposure times (10, 50 and 200 s) were obtained during revolution 2870, on January 17th, 2025. These images are shown in Fig. 11. The first image of 10 s was taken while the satellite had not yet stabilized its pointing, and is slightly offset on the X-axis by around 1 pixel.

Figure 11.- Set of raw OMC images around Cyg X-1, with different exposure times: 10 s (left), 50 s (middle) and 200 s (right).

A first inspection of the images shows that there are no dead/bright columns on the CCD, and that the saturation pattern on bright stars remains as expected. In Fig. 12, we compare the processed image of the Cyg X-1 field taken in 2025 (labeled as End of Life, EOL) with the reference image taken in 2002 (labeled as Beginning of Life, BOL). Note that the orientation is not the same, with a difference in the position angle of PA ~ 55 deg. In subsequent Figs. 13 – 15 we zoom on some parts of the image and modify the contrast to focus on some optical and photometric details.

Figure 12.- Zoom 1 on the Cyg X-1 field image. End of life (left), beginning of life (right). Note the similarity of both images, the only visual differences being due to the different position angles between them.

Figure 13.- Zoom 2 on the Cyg X-1 field image. End of life (left), beginning of life (right).

Figure 14.- Zoom 3 on the Cyg X-1 field image. End of life (left), beginning of life (right).

Figure 15.- Zoom on the Cyg X-1 field image with enhanced contrast to show the details of the background and the read out noise effect. End of life (left), beginning of life (right), different position angles. Note that the properties of the readout noise depends mainly on the temperature of the readout electronics, which is a function of the spacecraft attitude.

3.3 Additional images

We had the opportunity to obtain some additional OMC images before the end of the scientific operations of Integral and OMC: the PLATO LOPS2 field and M31, the Andromeda galaxy.

3.3.1 PLATO LOPS2 field

The PLATO mission has already selected its first Long Pointing Field, which is located in the Southern Hemisphere and is dubbed the LOPS2 field (Fig. 16). The OMC $5 \times 5 \text{ deg}^2$ images cover only the central part of the PLATO field, but will be used as reference to test the algorithms that are being developed for PLATO with real data. Indeed, both the angular pixel size and dynamic range of OMC and the individual PLATO telescopes are very similar ($15''$ for PLATO vs, $17''.5$ for OMC, saturation takes place in both cases at around $V=7-8$ mag, depending on exposure time). This set of reference images will be very useful to better understand the expected properties of the real PLATO images, and the performance of the different simulators being built.

The central coordinates of the PLATO LOPS2 field are:

RA [hms]: 06:21:14.5 ICRS (J2000)
 DEC [dms]: -47:53:13 ICRS (J2000)

Figure 16.- LOPS2 PLATO field on the Southern Hemisphere. The $5 \times 5 \text{ deg}^2$ area covered by OMC corresponds to the central part of the region covered simultaneously by the 24 “normal” PLATO cameras.

The following images were obtained during revolution 2870, on January 16th, 2025 (see Fig. 17):

- LOPS2 central field:
 - 12 images with exposures of 10, 50 and 200 s.
 - Problems:
 - first 3 images with wrong RA and DEC (one image taken during slewing),
 - 2 images with ~18 pixels offset,
 The remaining 7 images were well centered at LOPS2.
- Anomalies:
 - Slew failure to PID#22.
 - As a consequence PID#23 (LOPS2 Field pointing) was about 40 minutes behind schedule, which led to erroneous pointing during the time-tagged acquisition of the first images.

Figure 17.- Set of images on the PLATO LOPS2 field. Note that the image at the top right corner was obtained while the satellite was still slewing. Left column: 10 s exposures; middle column: 50 s exposures; right column: 200 s exposures.

Despite the loss of some images due to the late acquisition of the target field, we got enough images to process and create a high quality LOPS2 OMC image, which is shown in Fig. 18.

Figure 18.- Processed image of the PLATO LOPS2 field. Left: full $5 \times 5 \text{ deg}^2$ frame; top right: detail on individual stars, the saturated one is G Pup, an $V=5.76$ star; bottom right: position of the frame in the sky, within the central part of the PLATO LOPS2 field.

3.3.2 M31, the Andromeda galaxy

To celebrate the end of the scientific operations of OMC it was agreed with ESA (ISOC and MOC) to take a picture of an astronomical object of special relevance for outreach purposes. Considering the constraints on visibility, sensitivity, angular size and so on it was decided to take a set of images of M31, the Andromeda galaxy. The resulting composite image is shown in Fig. 19 with two different normalizations. While the rather large pixels of the OMC (17".5) do not allow to take very sharp images, OMC was able to obtain a beautiful picture of M31 together with its satellites galaxies M32 and M110. To obtain the final images shown in Fig. 19 a set of 15 shots with different exposure times (10, 50 and 200 s) was commanded during revolution 2885, on February 26th, 2025:

Figure 19.- OMC images of M31, the Andromeda galaxy, pictured with 2 different contrast scales. The left image allows to have an insight on the nuclear part of the galaxy, while the image on the right shows more details of the diffuse stellar arms and the dusty regions.

4 Discussion

4.1 Water ice condensation

It is known that the water vapor and other volatiles that materials and components can absorb during assembly on Earth, can gradually be released in the cold, low-pressure environment of space, and condense on the cold surfaces. Since the vapor pressure is in any case almost negligible, this condensation is a very slow process that can take several weeks or even months to complete. The optical cavity of the OMC focal plane assembly was purged with Nitrogen during its operations on ground, to minimize the amount of water vapor to be absorbed by the different materials within it, but this purging was dismantled when the OMC was integrated into the spacecraft, almost 2 years before launch.

The design of the OMC focal plane cavity makes the CCD to be the coldest surface within it, being directly attached to a cold finger with a direct thermal link to a dedicated radiator. As shown in Fig. 3 the temperature in the thermistor which is closer to the CCD has been below -60 C for the whole life of Integral, while the coolest thermistor on the lens barrel is thermostatically controlled within $-15 \pm 5\text{ C}$. As a consequence, the CCD surface acts as a cool trap and tends to attract any volatile molecule “flying” within the focal plane cavity, even if the temperatures are much above the ice sublimation limit in open vacuum.

To avoid the condensation of volatiles just after launch, when the outgassing from different elements was highest, we operated the CCD baking heater during 2.6 days as soon as control of the spacecraft was achieved. The Flat-Field matrix derived during revolution 2, after this bakeout and before the OMC cover was open, is shown in Fig. 20 (left). The FF matrix derived during laboratory tests on the ground is also plotted for comparison (right). Both matrices are indeed very similar, though the one taken in space shows a larger amount of deposited particles.

Figure 20- OMC Flat-Field matrices. Left: during revolution 2, after the initial bakeout; right: on-ground during laboratory calibration. The dark points correspond to particles deposited on the surface of the CCD.

While most of the molecules should have left the cavity through the venting holes during launch, when exposed to vacuum, a small amount of vapor molecules must have remained inside it, and condensed slowly on the CCD surface as discussed above. Nevertheless we want to stress that, while Fig. 4 shows highly structured and intricate maps of pixel to pixel relative sensitivities due to the effect of the contamination affecting the transparency, the absolute effect remained within $\pm 2.5\%$ for most of the pixels, as shown in Fig. 21.

Figure 21.- Histograms of the Flat-Field matrix corresponding to revolution 1971 (mid 2018), which is representative of the contamination once it stabilized. Top: log scale; bottom: linear scale. The vertical red dotted lines show that the relative sensitivity of most of the CCD pixels remained within $RS \sim \pm 0.025$ (2.5%) after stabilization, despite the effect of ice condensation (being RS the relative pixel to pixel sensitivity).

In Fig. 22 the improvement in the relative sensitivities of the different pixels is evident, with a much narrower distribution after the bakeout (note this Figure is in log scale). But just after 5 weeks, the re-condensation of volatiles on the CCD surface led to a rather broad distribution of relative sensitivities, as shown in Fig. 23, indicating that the re-condensation started very fast. Indeed, repetition on around a monthly basis of the de-icing procedures has also been required for other missions, like for the WFPC2 on HST, hosting CCDs with similar technology and working at similar temperatures than the OMC.

Figure 22.- Comparison of Flat-Field histograms (log scale) for revolutions 2871 (before baking) and 2873 (after baking).

Figure 23.- Comparison of Flat-Field histograms (log scale) for revolutions 2873 (just after baking) and 2886 (5 weeks after baking).

It is interesting to note that the distribution of the relative sensitivities of most of the pixels showed a rather symmetrical profile after 22 years of operation, as evident from Fig. 21 (bottom). The skewness of the profile shown in Fig. 21 (top) is an artifact of the logarithmic scale used, and indeed it affects only a very small fraction of the pixels (mostly those on which micron size dust particulates accumulated decreasing their transparency). The distribution became much narrower after bakeout (see Fig. 22). But the profiles of the histograms of revolutions 2871 (condensation stabilized after 22 years) and 2886 (condensation just proceeding after the last bakeout) are completely different when compared to the histogram of the “clean” CCD at revolution 2873. Indeed, the distribution is more symmetrical but much broader for revolution 2886 (though the logarithmic scale tends to stress the effect on a relatively small number of pixels). As discussed above the effect of condensation does not seem to be a linear, uniform loss of transparency over the CCD, as other missions have experienced, but the different thickness of ice on different locations, combined with the use of a V filter, leads to a rather large distribution of relative transparencies, i.e, of relative pixel sensitivities. We believe this effect is at the root of the strange, still not well understood, behavior of the OMC CCD during the first 2 years, with the pixels in the center and in the periphery of the CCD alternating relative sensitivities as the condensation of new molecules took place.

Finally, we compare in Fig. 24 the Flat-Field histograms corresponding to the on-ground calibration and to revolution 2873, just after the last bakeout in orbit. While the overall shape of both histograms is similar, there was an almost complete lack of hot pixels at the beginning of the operations. The excess in the 2783 histogram bins around ~0.9 is due to the remaining contamination patterns on the Flat-Field image, even after de-icing.

Figure 24.- Comparison of Flat-Field histograms (log scale) corresponding to the on-ground calibration and to revolution 2873, just after the last bakeout.

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Summarizing, our technical tests have shown that:

- Even at temperatures above the ice sublimation limit in open vacuum, water and other volatiles molecules originated from outgassing will condense on the coldest surface of the instruments in a closed enclosure.
- A “baking” heater installed close to this cold surface allows to remove very efficiently the ice that could have condensed on it. In principle, the affected surface should be heated to a temperature clearly above the temperature of other surfaces within the cavity. In the case of OMC the temperature of the lens barrel during the de-icing was around 0 deg, so that a temperature above +20C was required.
- But if the design of the cavity is essentially closed, except for the venting holes, as is the case of the OMC, the sublimated molecules will not escape from the enclosure and will end up depositing again on the cold surface. Repeating the activity could force the molecules to escape the focal plane cavity through the venting holes or through any other path to open space; however, we have not had the opportunity to repeat this process several times to confirm this point on the OMC. A small trend in this sense, if any, has been reported by other missions performing de-icing procedures, like for the WFPC2 on HST. On Euclid, ice is condensing again on the cold surfaces some time after each de-icing activity, with no statistics yet to verify whether this de-icing would be progressively more efficient with time.
- In a more open design, the molecules would probably escape from the volume of interest and would be released to open space (or to other external cold surfaces trapping them).
- In any case, we expect a significant thermoelastic stress on the CCD/cold finger/radiator support structures after a steep temperature increase from -80 C to + 40 C in a relatively short time (less than 2 hr from -80 C to +20C), and back (6 hr) at the end of the activity. This should be taken into account if periodic de-icing activities become necessary for other instruments experiencing the same problem.

4.2 OMC image quality

We have continuously monitored the image quality and performance of the OMC during the Integral scientific operations. The average Point Spread Function (PSF) of the whole system (optics + detector) was very stable along the lifetime of the instrument, with a measured PSF to be $PSF = 1.3 \pm 0.1$ pixels. Nevertheless, we identified a clear correlation between the PSF and the temperature of the lens barrel, as shown in Fig. 25 (left). The temperature of the lens barrel was indeed identified as the main factor affecting the PSF over the 22⁺ years of OMC operations.

Figure 25.- Left: Example of the correlation found between the OMC Point Spread Function (PSF) with the thermostatically controlled lens barrel temperatures. Right: Image of a single star showing the effective size of the PSF on the CCD. The x-axis is labelled in IJDs.

We have analyzed in detail the reference images taken on the Cyg X-1 field comparing them with the ones taken during the commissioning phase in 2002, as discussed in Sect. 3.2. Figs. 12 and 13 show that the saturation patterns in both set of images remain constant, with almost no differences. Moreover, Fig. 14 shows that the optical performance of the OMC remains also stable after 22⁺ years in space. Fig. 25 (right) highlights that the PSF of the system remains still around $PSF = 1.3 \pm 0.1$ pixels, as monitored during the calibration runs. Finally, Fig. 15 shows that the RMS readout noise is also similar in both images, with the 2025 image displaying even less structure than the one observed at the beginning of the mission (this is not a result of the ageing of the electronics, but depends mostly on the temperature of the readout electronics).

No obvious differences are seen visually between both set of images, indicating that the sensitivity of the system has not degraded significantly. We have plotted in Fig. 26 (left) the evolution of the zero point of the calibration, which is a proxy of the photometrical sensitivity of the whole system, computed and monitored continuously by comparison with the observations of a large set of photometric standard stars (Fig. 26 right). It can be seen that the overall loss of sensitivity since revolution 400 has been only around 3% (the oscillations before that revolution are due to the effects of the condensation of molecular material on the surface of the CCD during the first 3 years, but we can not explain them yet very well). This indicates that the darkening of the optical lenses, and especially of the first optical elements (the protective window and the filters), has been very modest considering the time spent in space and the lack of protection to the high-energy radiation. This demonstrates the convenience of using radiation-hard glasses for the lenses for long-lasting space missions.

Figure 26.- Evolution of the OMC absolute photometric calibration. Left: evolution of the zero point of the calibration; right: visualization of the zero point determination process during a calibration run. This is done by comparing the catalog V magnitudes of the photometric stars with their total counts as derived from the OSA OMC pipeline.

In Fig. 27 we show the evolution of the number of “bad” pixels (those with sensitivity < 0.8, mostly affected by the deposition of particles on the CCD surface) and of “hot” pixels (with dark current up to a factor 2 higher than the average sky background). All in all the number of pixels that show some degradation remain very small after 22⁺ years, compared to the total number of pixels of the CCD (above 1 million). We can therefore conclude that the degradation of the CCD performance has been very small after 22⁺ years of operation in space, certainly due to the high level of shielding vs. the external high energy radiation provided by the set of lenses just in front of the CCD and the massive Integral spacecraft behind it.

Figure 27.- Evolution of the number of “bad” pixels (left) and “hot” pixels (right)

4.3 CCD dark current

We have also analyzed the evolution of the CCD dark current during the Integral operational lifetime, as plotted in Fig. 28. Despite being exposed to high energy radiation during more than 22 years, the dark current of the OMC CCD has remained at relatively low values. It has been only after the Critical Mission Anomaly experienced in September 2021 that both the value and the dispersion of the dark current increased more significantly, but it remained in any case around 2 digital counts per pixel in average for 200 s exposures, for a total of 4096 digital counts per pixel (ADC works with 12 bits).

Figure 28.- Evolution of the dark current. Note the increase in the average dark current and in its dispersion after the Mission Critical Anomaly on Sept. 22nd, 2021, marked with the vertical blue line. The reasons for this are still unknown.

In Fig. 29 we have represented the measured dark current vs. the temperature at the cold finger, the closest point to the CCD itself. The colour scale indicates the date ranges. Red is the end of the scientific operations, violet the start.

While the lower envelope of temperatures has remained more or less stable (corresponding to the cold attitude of the S/C), the upper envelope has increased with time by few degrees. Temperatures above -68C have been reached only after IJD~7.000. This is a combination of a lower efficiency of the radiator with time and the change of operations when the z-flip control system was introduced in Integral, with a larger fraction of hot cases. This could explain the large amplitude of the oscillations in dark current after rev. 2400 shown in Fig. 28.

Figure 29.- Dark current measurements as a function of CCD temperature (as measured on the cold finger). The color scale indicates the evolution with time. The black circle corresponds to the calibration just after the de-icing (revolution 2873), while the black square corresponds to the last observations taken with OMC few weeks after (revolution 2886).

The two measurements made at the end of the mission show clearly smaller dark currents, when compared to measurements at similar temperature taken in the last years. But in any case the values are not so low as they were at the beginning of the mission for the same temperatures.

We conclude that baking the CCD has apparently decreased its dark current, but only to a certain extent, not recovering the original values.

5 Conclusions

The Integral mission was launched from Baikonur on Oct. 17th, 2002. Scientific operations started in January 2003, after a successful commissioning phase, and ended in March 2025, after more than 22 years of almost continuous activity. Some technical problems during this time were brilliantly solved by the ESA engineering team, making it possible to extend the operations much longer than expected at the launch time. In order to comply with the new regulations on safe spacecraft disposal at the end of their lifetime, a maneuver was performed in early 2015 to assure that Integral will re-enter on the Pacific ocean in February 2029, whatever happens until then.

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The Optical Monitoring Camera (OMC) on Integral has proven to be a very robust instrument. The only anomaly it experienced was the lost of the main power supply chain after an Emergency Safe Attitude Mode (ESAM), followed by a Critical Mission Anomaly (CMA), in September 2021, but the power supply was switched to the redundant unit with normal operations since then.

A set of technical tests have been performed before switching off the instrument to verify the performance of the instrument by comparing with reference images taken during the commissioning phase. Furthermore, the de-icing procedure has been tested by activating the baking heaters during almost 3 days. OMC was designed with this capability of de-icing, but it was never performed during the operational phase because it was considered too risky (the thermoelastic stress induced by the sudden increase of temperature could have led to damages on the support interfaces) and, specially, because it was not clear that this baking would permanently remove the contaminating molecules from the focal plane cavity.

The de-icing was performed on January 20st, 2025 by activating the heater during 2.7 days. As a result of it, most of the condensation on the surface of the CCD disappeared and the flat-field became much “flatter” by a factor above 5. Nevertheless, and as expected, a new calibration performed 5 weeks after showed that the volatile molecules were already starting to condense again on the surface of the CCD, which indeed is the coldest surface within the focal plane cavity, acting therefore as a cold trap. A continuous repetition of this procedure could have led to the complete removal of contaminants forcing them to escape through the venting holes, but the impact of repeated baking activities could have led to permanent damages on the CCD support structure interfaces. Since the condensation stabilized after some time, allowing us to correct the rather non-uniform flat-field of the CCD, we conclude that it was safer not to activate the baking heater and to continue with a rough but stable and well characterized Flat-Field.

The optical performance of the OMC has remained very stable during the last 22⁺ years. The continuous monitoring and calibration of the instrument during this time had already shown that the sensitivity has decreased by just a mere 3-4%, indicating the radiation-hard lenses have not been affected by a significant darkening induced by radiation. Furthermore, the optical performance has remained also very stable, with a Point Spread Function (PSF) within 1.3 ± 0.1 pixels throughout the 22⁺ years of operations. The CCD itself has also withstood the harsh space conditions in pretty good shape: the average dark current has increased, as well as the number of hot pixels, but no columns have been lost and it has continued to provide high quality data until the last day. Finally, baking the CCD has apparently decreased its dark current, but only to a certain extent, not recovering the original values

We have confirmed the OMC performance after 22⁺ years by comparing a picture of the Cyg X-1 region with a similar image taken during the commissioning phase. Despite the internal ageing effects of the CCD, the visual inspection of both images does not show any significant difference. If any, the CCD readout noise temporal structure is significantly cleaner in the image of 2025 than in the original one from 2002.

We have also taken the opportunity that the first long pointing field to be observed by the PLATO mission was visible by Integral in February 2025 to take a reference image of its central $5 \times 5 \text{ deg}^2$

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region, the one which will be observed simultaneously by the PLATO 24 “normal” telescopes. The similarities between OMC and PLATO in terms of pixel angular size and saturation limit makes this image very useful to test the processing and extraction algorithms being defined for PLATO on real, similar data taken by OMC.

Finally, we took the opportunity to get a beautiful image of M31, the Andromeda galaxy, for legacy outreach of the Integral Optical Monitoring Camera.

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Annex: Revolution number vs. date.

Revolution	Date
01	17/10/2002
10	15/11/2002
37	01/02/2003
67	01/05/2003
98	02/08/2003
129	03/11/2003
159	01/02/2004
190	03/05/2004
220	01/08/2004
251	02/11/2004
282	03/02/2005
312	03/05/2005
342	01/08/2005
373	02/11/2005
404	02/02/2006
434	03/05/2006
464	01/08/2006
495	01/11/2006
526	02/02/2007
556	03/05/2007
586	01/08/2007
617	01/11/2007
648	02/02/2008
678	02/05/2008
709	03/08/2008
740	03/11/2008
770	01/02/2009
800	02/05/2009
831	03/08/2009
862	03/11/2009
892	01/02/2010
922	02/05/2010
953	03/08/2010
984	03/11/2010
1014	01/02/2011
1044	02/05/2011
1075	02/08/2011
1106	03/11/2011
1136	01/02/2012
1166	01/05/2012
1197	01/08/2012
1228	02/11/2012
1259	03/02/2013
1288	01/05/2013
1319	01/08/2013
1350	02/11/2013

Revolution	Date
1381	03/02/2014
1410	01/05/2014
1441	01/08/2014
1472	02/11/2014
1503	02/02/2015
1537	03/05/2015
1571	02/08/2015
1606	03/11/2015
1640	01/02/2016
1674	01/05/2016
1709	03/08/2016
1743	01/11/2016
1778	02/02/2017
1811	01/05/2017
1846	02/08/2017
1881	03/11/2017
1915	01/02/2018
1949	03/05/2018
1983	01/08/2018
2018	02/11/2018
2052	01/02/2019
2086	02/05/2019
2121	03/08/2019
2155	01/11/2019
2190	03/02/2020
2224	03/05/2020
2258	01/08/2020
2293	02/11/2020
2327	01/02/2021
2361	02/05/2021
2395	01/08/2021
2430	02/11/2021
2465	03/02/2022
2498	02/05/2022
2533	03/08/2022
2567	01/11/2022
2602	02/02/2023
2635	01/05/2023
2670	02/08/2023
2704	01/11/2023
2739	02/02/2024
2773	02/05/2024
2807	01/08/2024
2842	02/11/2024
2877	03/02/2025
2886	28/02/2025

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Figure A1.- Integral revolution number vs. year. Note the change of slope after the maneuver performed in early 2015 to modify the orbit assuring a reentry in February 2029.